

The distribution of the median in an even sample

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Abstract

The probability density function of the median in a sample of even size is not well known, and an expression is difficult to find in the literature. This note gives a straightforward derivation that uses a number of foundational concepts and also gives a derivation from an intermediate equation.

Introduction

Consider drawing an independent sample of size n from a distribution with probability density function (pdf) $f(x)$ and (cumulative) distribution function (cdf) $F(x)$. If $n = 2m + 1$ then the sample median is equal to one of the order statistics, and this facilitates the derivation of its pdf. However, if $n = 2m$ then, by definition, the median of the sample is the arithmetic mean of the m th and $(m + 1)$ th order statistics, and the pdf of the sample median is not obtainable in the same way. In fact, an expression for the pdf of the median when n is even is remarkably hard to find in the literature. For $n = 2m$, Cho and Cho (2013) have given the result

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x) = \frac{4m}{B(m, m)} \int_0^\infty f(x-y) f(x+y) F(x-y)^{m-1} [1-F(x+y)]^{m-1} dy, \quad (1)$$

with $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ the beta function. They derived (1) using the concept of the number of possible orderings of the data, and their argument was not detailed. Also, the text of Rohatgi and Saleh (2015, pp.259–260) gives the equivalent expression

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x) = \frac{2(2m)!}{[(m-1)!]^2} \int_x^\infty F(2x-v)^{m-1} [1-F(v)]^{m-1} f(2x-v) f(v) dv \quad (2)$$

but without a derivation or a reference. This author has not seen the result published anywhere else. In this note, we derive the same result using a number of basic undergraduate concepts — the transformation of variables, conditional probability, and truncated distributions — and we also derive it from an existing expression for the joint distribution of a pair of order statistics.

Analysis

In a sample of size n with (random) order statistics obeying $X_{(1)} \leq X_{(2)} \cdots \leq X_{(n)}$, the median is defined to be

$$\hat{X} \equiv \begin{cases} X_{(m+1)} & n = 2m + 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} (X_{(m)} + X_{(m+1)}) & n = 2m. \end{cases}$$

If each element of the sample is obtained independently from a distribution with pdf $f(x)$ and cdf $F(x)$ then, when n is odd, the pdf of the sample median is

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x) = \frac{1}{B(m+1, m+1)} f(x) F(x)^m [1-F(x)]^m \quad n = 2m + 1. \quad (3)$$

This follows immediately from the pdf of the j th order statistic $X_{(j)}$, which is well-known to be (David and Nagaraja, 2003, eq. 2.1.6)

$$f_{X_{(j)}}(x) = \frac{1}{B(j, n-j+1)} f(x) F(x)^{j-1} [1-F(x)]^{n-j}. \quad (4)$$

However, no closed-form expression like (3) exists for the pdf of the median when n is even. Instead, we can derive the pdf as an integral in two ways as follows.

(i) Suppose $n = 2m$. On the condition that $X_{(m+1)} = a$, the median \hat{X} is the random variable $(X_{(m)} + a)/2$ and the conditional pdf of \hat{X} is

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x | X_{(m+1)} = a) = \begin{cases} 2f_{X_{(m)}}(2x - a | X_{(m+1)} = a) & x \leq a \\ 0 & x > a. \end{cases}$$

However, on this condition, the variables $X_{(1)}, \dots, X_{(m)}$ are distributed randomly over all values of $x \leq a$ according to the pdf $f(x)$. So the conditional distribution of $X_{(m)}$ is the distribution of the largest of an independent sample of size m drawn randomly from the truncated distribution with pdf $f(x)/F(a)$ for $x \leq a$. Therefore, the conditional cdf of $X_{(m)}$ is

$$F_{X_{(m)}}(z | X_{(m+1)} = a) = \left(\frac{F(z)}{F(a)} \right)^m \quad z \leq a,$$

meaning that the conditional pdf of $X_{(m)}$ is

$$f_{X_{(m)}}(z | X_{(m+1)} = a) = m f(z) F(z)^{m-1} \left(\frac{1}{F(a)} \right)^m \quad z \leq a.$$

This implies that

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x | X_{(m+1)} = a) = \begin{cases} 2m f(2x - a) F(2x - a)^{m-1} \left(\frac{1}{F(a)} \right)^m & x \leq a \\ 0 & x > a. \end{cases}$$

Therefore, the unconditional pdf of \hat{X} is

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x) = 2m \int_x^\infty f(2x - a) F(2x - a)^{m-1} \left(\frac{1}{F(a)} \right)^m f_{X_{(m+1)}}(a) da.$$

Using (4) with $j = m + 1$, we obtain

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x) = \frac{2(2m)!}{[(m-1)!]^2} \int_x^\infty f(2x - a) F(2x - a)^{m-1} f(a) [1 - F(a)]^{m-1} da,$$

which corresponds to expression (2). On setting $y = a - x$ and rearranging terms we obtain the final result for the pdf of the median of a sample of size $2m$,

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x) = K \int_0^\infty f(x-y) f(x+y) F(x-y)^{m-1} [1-F(x+y)]^{m-1} dy,$$

where

$$K = \frac{2(2m)!}{[(m-1)!]^2} = 2m^2 \binom{2m}{m} = \frac{4m}{B(m, m)},$$

in agreement with (1).

(ii) The result can also be derived from a standard expression for the joint density function of two order statistics (David and Nagaraja, 2003, eq. 2.2.1)

$$f_{X_{(r)}, X_{(s)}}(u, v) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(s-r-1)!(n-s)!} f(u) f(v) F(u)^{r-1} [F(v)-F(u)]^{s-r-1} [1-F(v)]^{n-s}.$$

With $n = 2m$, $r = m$ and $s = m + 1$, this becomes

$$f_{X_{(m)}, X_{(m+1)}}(u, v) = \frac{(2m)!}{[(m-1)!]^2} f(u) f(v) F(u)^{m-1} [1-F(v)]^{m-1}.$$

Putting $x = (u+v)/2$ and $y = (v-u)/2$, integrating over y from 0 to $+\infty$ and doubling the result to account for the integral from $-\infty$ to 0 gives (1).

References

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